
Towards an Improved Resilient Business Model for Cooperative Financial Institutions in Kenya

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Abstract

Developing countries whose economies are supported mostly by small, medium enterprises need a resilient and sustainable financial ecosystem including CFIs that will resist systemic shocks and disruptions from pandemics such as the COVID-19 pandemic. This article investigates the post COVID-19 pandemic resilience of Cooperative Financial Institutions (CFIs) in Kenya with the purpose of formulating and proposing an improved resilient business model for CFIs during times of systemic economic shocks and crises. This study utilizes an exploratory descriptive mixed cross-sectional study design with a mixed methods approach. The researcher interviewed 44 respondents consisting of operations, finance, and marketing officers and Chief Executive Officers in Nairobi County. Secondary data was generated from the existing documents in the respective institutions. Pearson's Chi-square test and logistic regression aided in showing the associations between the dependent and independent variables using Statistical Package for Social Sciences version 23 for quantitative data. A confidence interval of 95% was considered statistically significant. Interpretative Phenomenological Analysis (IPA) of the participant's responses identified five critical success factors that facilitated the CFIs resilience and success during the pandemic, namely technology, status of membership, quick adaptability, open mindedness and effective communication. This study's contribution to the body of knowledge forms the basis for re-planning to concur the effects of pandemics in the future as well as repositioning in resource mobilization, adopting workable technology, context-specific mechanisms to enhance continuity regardless of the pandemic or any other eventualities that may influence the operation of businesses negatively.

Keywords: Cooperative financial institutions, Covid-19 pandemic, resilience, critical success factors

Introduction

The occurrence of COVID-19 pandemic entirely infiltrated the operations of CFIs operations and business development. The Covid-19 pandemic caused unprecedented disruptions to global supply chains, impacted financial consumers, and caused challenges to access and use financial services in the cooperative movement in unprecedented ways (European Commission, 2020). Even with the returning of normalcy, globally, the impact of COVID-19 remains the most cross-cutting financial catastrophe of all industries (Giese & Haldane, 2020). Prior to the Covid-19 the CFI business model had shown relative resilience to major shocks like the 2007-2008 global financial crisis (Birchall, 2013). This resilience stemmed from several advantages inherent to the cooperative business model, including ownership, control, and member interests. Furthermore, innovation, collective skills and the role of government are additional advantages that contribute to the resilience of cooperatives (Borda-Rodriguez & Vicari, 2012). However, Allen and Maghimbi (2009) warn that evidence from the 2007-2008 financial crisis shows that financial cooperatives in Africa are not strong enough to protect themselves against systemic shocks, especially those that result in loss of income for their members. Hence, the operations of CFIs in Africa remain heavily affected by the continent's stagnated economy even as global financial institutions are experiencing post pandemic recovery.

Institutionalizing resilient African CFIs post COVID-19 is an antidote for accelerating preparedness and response to economic crises, financial instability and human capital losses. Thus, this study investigates the extent that CFIs in Kenya, referred to as Savings and Credit Cooperatives (SACCOs) have adapted and reengineered their business models, and how they can better insulate themselves in the future. The article firstly identifies the notable pandemic-era changes experienced by CFIs ranging from staffing changes, technological advances to the introduction of new products. Secondly the article assesses the critical success factors and survival mechanisms for the cooperative financial institutions post COVID-19 in Kenya. The article identifies technology, status of membership, quick adaptability, open mindedness and effective communication as the critical success factors that acted as survival mechanisms for CFI's.

Methodology

This study was conducted in Nairobi County which hosts Kenya capital where the majority of CFIs in the country are domiciled there, whether head offices, liaison offices or marketing offices. The researcher selected the CFIs through stratified random sampling to identify active CFIs from the State Department of Cooperatives' (SDC) records. The SDC's records were corroborated with information from Kenya Union of Savings and Credit Cooperative (KUSCCO) Ltd, and Sacco Societies Regulatory Authority (SASRA). The researcher subsequently utilized purposive sampling considered sampling four strata including Agriculture sector, community based, Service sector, and government units allied CFIs. In all the CFIs that participated, heads of departments were purposely selected to participate. Proportionate representative samples of both CFIs and participants were calculated and allocated across the study institutions to allow for representation and generalizability.

This study adopted an analytical cross-sectional study that employed a mixed method of both quantitative and qualitative data collection and analysis methods. Personal Data Assistants (PDAs) obtained quantitative data through administration of 35 questionnaires. The questions focused on the Cooperative Financial institutions pre, during and post COVID-19 pandemic. The PDA's administered the questionnaires to a sample population of managers,

including operations officers, credit officers, finance/accounts officers, and customer relations from the selected cooperative financial institutions as stratified across the county based on the sectors and sub-counties in proportionate manner.

Table 1. Coverage of the Quantitative Surveys

CFI	Category	Departments	n
Acumen SACCO	Tourism and Hospitality	Head of credit, Finance and Accounts	2
Afya SACCO	Health	Head of Marketing, other technical officer	2
Asili SACCO	Banking and Finance	Head of finance and accounts	1
Barabara SACCO	Road Construction	Other Technical Officer	1
BAT SACCO	Agribusiness	Head of finance and accounts	1
Cereal Growers Association SACCO	Agriculture	Other Technical Officer	1
Harambe SACCO	Multisectoral	Head of operations and head of marketing	2
Java WDV SACCO	Hospitality	Head of Operations	1
Stima SACCO	Energy	Head of Marketing, and Head of Credit	2
Ushuru SACCO	Revenue	Head of Credit, finance and other technical officer.	2
Utabibu SACCO	Health	Head of Operations, Credit and Other technical Officer	3
Police SACCO	Security, Law and Order	Head of credit and finance and accounts	2
Magereza SACCO	Correction	Head of operations and head of marketing	2
Ardhi SACCO	Land	Head of operations and other technical officer	3
Postbank SACCO	Tele-Communication	Head of operations, head of Credit and head of accounts and finance	3
Kenyatta University SACCO	Education	Head of customer care, another technical officer	2
Makataba SACCO	Finance	Head of operations and head of marketing	1
Kenyatta Matibabu SACCO	Health	Head of credit, finance and accounts and other technical officer	3
Total			35

Quantitative data analysis was analyzed via parametric and non- parametric statistical inferential methods and adopted three methods of presenting them including exploratory analysis via descriptive analysis of central tendency i.e (mean, mode and median); graphically; distribution (frequencies and dispersion) standard deviation and inferential statistics to test hypothesis of the study in addition to making tangible conclusions in more quantifiable way. The Pearson's Chi-square test and logistic regression aided in showing the associations between the dependent and independent variables. A p-value of < 0.05 was considered statistically significant. Both tables, graphs and charts were used to present categorical data in a statistical manner and with clear quantification as well as substantiating

quantitatively. This is essential in presenting quantitative statistical data for informed and evidence-based decision making.

The researcher obtained qualitative data using Key Informant Interviews with 11 senior CFI staff members. The key informants included the Chairperson of Executive Committees; Chairperson of Supervisory Committees; and County Directors of Cooperatives from the sampled CFI's. The table below outlines the distribution of the key informants.

Table 2. Coverage of the Qualitative Interviews

CFI	Category of CFI	Number of participants
Acumen SACCO	Tourism and Hospitality	1
Afya SACCO	Health	1
Asili SACCO	Banking and Finance	1
Barabara SACCO	Road Construction	1
BAT SACCO	Agribusiness	1
Cereal Growers Association SACCO	Agriculture	1
Harambe Sacco	Multisectoral	1
Java WDV SACCO	Hospitality	1
Stima SACCO	Energy	1
Ushuru SACCO	Revenue	1
Utabibu SACCO	Health	1
Total		11

11 out of the 46 licensed deposits taking CFIs located in Nairobi Metropolitan City participated in the study. This number represents a 22% response which meets Mugenda and Mugenda (2003) 10% response rate threshold for adequate for analysis and in representation across all the institutions. However, due to unprecedented challenges including time and study period which took place in the months of December, 2023 and March 2024, the busiest months of CFIs. During these months, the CFIs were engaged in Annual General Meetings (AGMs), declaration of dividends and other managerial meetings.

The researcher used NVivo version 12 to analyze the qualitative data. This data was analyzed using content analysis by categorization, summarization and comparison on the emerging responses. These findings were triangulated with quantitative as per the themes and samples of verbatim recordings were directly documented as narrated by the participants in an anonymous way and structured substantive conclusions and recommendations were drawn from the study.

A robust desk review was done to collect relevant secondary data to reinforce the primary data. Secondary data sources included both published and unpublished documents that existed at the institutions and county offices in charge of cooperative institutions including recent reports, internal policies, and manuscripts, including financial reports. Additionally, the study participants provided additional documents and factsheets for perusal and for familiarization with their operations and services and some with statistics on the performance and specific data that facilitated the identification of other targets.

Ethical Considerations

The research required in-depth semi structured interviews and survey questionnaires with respondents for data collection. Hence, the research was required to comply with the

University of Kwa-Zulu Natal's (UKZN) Ethics Code of Conduct regarding human subjects. Interviews, therefore, were only conducted after the researcher had received authorization from the Humanities and Social Sciences Research Ethics Committee reference HSSREC/00006356/2023.

In consideration of the interests and wellbeing of the participants and society as a priority, the researcher adhered to the following standards based on the Belmont Report:

- **Informed consent**
Prior to interviews, the researcher secured administrative clearance from the participating cooperative financial institutions during the entry process which was preceded with courtesy calls and visitations as well as official letters sent to the institutions explaining the aim of the study. Additionally, the researcher would verbally outline the informed consent conditions in the respondent's preferred language. All interview subjects granted permission for the interviews to be recorded.
- **Assessment of risks and benefits**
This researcher assured the participants that they would be safeguarding measures implemented to protect them against discrimination of whatever form.
- **Confidentiality**
The researcher maintained a high standard of confidentiality, privacy and anonymity to protect the identities of the interview subjects.

Findings

The Covid-19 pandemic's primary negative impacts on CFIs in Kenya have included financial strain, stemming from increased credit risk and deteriorating asset quality. Additionally, the economic disruptions caused by the pandemic, including business closures, job losses, and reduced consumer spending, have led to a surge in loan defaults and delinquencies. The findings in this article presented below focuses on how CFIs in Kenya adapt their operations rapidly to comply with health and safety measures and ensure business continuity.

Notable Changes During Covid-19

The section begins with identifying the main organizational changes implemented by the sampled SACCOs such as staffing changes and introducing new products.

Human Capital

The study investigated what might have changed on the staff due to the pandemic. The results of the inquiries are summarized in Table 3. Some of the most notable changes on staff included recruiting additional staff, adapting to remote working technology, introducing social distancing and increased salaries and increasing turnover rate among others.

Table 3: Changes in Human Capital

Category	Frequency	Percentage
Having to learn remote working technologies	5	15.29
Additional Staff	5	14.29
Remote working and/Social distancing	4	11.43
Increased salaries	4	11.43
Vaccination	4	11.43
Voluntary retirement or resignation	3	8.57
Increased sense of ownership	3	8.57
Trainings/capacity building	3	8.57
Increased health awareness	3	8.57
Covid-19 Insurance	2	5.71
Performance contracting	1	2.86
Dissatisfaction	1	2.86

Membership

A further inquiry into some of the major changes which might have been necessitated may the pandemic on membership have been summarized in Table 4. Most of the SACCOs (42.0%) noted growth of membership, while 20.0% noted reduction in membership. Only 8.57% CFIs noted that their members became more enlightened on matters of consumer.

Table 4: Changes on Membership

Categories	Frequency	Percentage
Growth of membership	15	42.86
Decline in membership	7	17.14
Members adopted technology	3	8.57
Reduced savings	2	5.71
Decline in rate of growth	1	2.86
Dormant accounts increased	1	2.86
Members promoted to in civil service	1	2.86
Members are more informed about the SACCO	1	2.86

Technology

The participants noted the pandemic necessitated the advancement in both operation technology, and service delivery technology. Some of the operation technologies included Google meet, zoom, or team to facilitate virtual meetings. Service delivery technologies on the other hand included mobile services, online banking, online application of membership, or credit facilities, mobile Apps among others. These technologies were part of business continuity strategies. The research findings 34.29% of SACCOs adopted new technologies for service delivery while another equal proportion adopted both service delivery and operations technologies. Additionally, 14.29% of the CFIs adopted technology specifically to enhance their operations. 5 SACCOs representing 17.14% of the study population did not submit responses on this section.

New Products

The findings indicate that SACCOs introduced certain products and services amidst efforts to recover and to increase their business resilience. Almost all the CFIs (94.29%) noted that they had introduced a new line of product. A further interrogation on the specific products introduced, they highlighted various products as summarized in Table 5.

Table 5: New Products Introduced

Category	Frequency	Percentage
Additional credit facilities	16	45.71
Additional credit facilities - long terms	6	17.14
Additional credit facilities - digital	4	11.43
Saving products	2	5.17
Additional credit facilities with flexible repayment schedule	1	2.86
Asset financing	1	2.86
Extension of loan repayment to 120 months	1	2.86
Insurance	1	2.86
Loan insurance	1	2.86
Missing	2	5.71
Total	35	100

Almost a similar trend was observed with regards to the new services introduced amidst or after the pandemic. 82.86% of the participants acknowledged addition of new services with the automation services topping the list (42.86%). Table 6 below, outlines the new services that were introduced.

Table 6: New Services

Category	Frequency	Percentage
Automation of services	15	42.86
Automation of services and operations	4	11.43
Insurance	3	8.57
Alternative mobile banking	1	2.86
Change of terms for some of our loan products	1	2.86
Merchant pay bill services	1	2.86
New CRM channels	1	2.86
SACCO link VISA ATMs and M-Sacco	1	2.86
Salary processing and Easy cash for members	1	2.86
Missing	6	17.14
Total	35	100

Critical Success Factors

The managers and/or their representatives were asked to highlight what they considered to have been their survival secret or otherwise the critical success factors especially during the pandemic. The study population identified technology, status of membership, quick adaptability, open mindedness and effective communication as the main survival mechanisms that potentially enhanced the SACCOs' post-pandemic resilience.

Technological adaptation

The findings indicate that two dimensions of technology emerged as critical success factors. Firstly, there were operational technologies and service delivery technologies. Operational technologies are those technologies which were adopted or advanced by the management team to run the operations of the CFI's. The sentiments below, indicated the scope and success of operations technology adoptions as noted by the managers.

“So for us on a positive note, yes, it accelerated adoption of technology. At board I've also mentioned to you that now we were using e-board as opposed to the traditional physical meeting. So it did, it did in a big way” (KIIVII)

“Governance shifted towards virtual meetings and electronic voting to comply with social distancing measures. Committees continued to function remotely, ensuring continuity in decision-making processes.” (KIIVI)

Secondly, service delivery technologies were also advanced or adopted to ensure continuity with service delivery to the customers. Additionally, such technologies also facilitated the adherence of the government's guidelines on mitigation measures against the spread of the disease. As one participant noted below,

“So, yeah, that's part of the technology that we created. They changed a bit. What also changed is how now to deliver services using technology. What I kept on saying, focusing on mobile lending, just to keep on driving, driving sales” (KII V).

Status of Membership

The status of membership refers to the nature of the employment contracts and industry and occupations held by the SACCOs' members. The findings indicate that CFIs whose membership was mainly composed of government employees were more stable because they did neither suffer from job losses nor pay cuts. They also noted that people in formal employment generally neither defaulted nor delayed on loan repayment because in most cases, their repayment was done on check off system. Conversely members in the self-employment or informal sector suffered the greatest impacts of the pandemic because of the lockdowns, curfews and the social distancing restrictions which were in enforcement during the pandemic. The mitigation measures forced some members out of business, of reduced business operation hours all of which translated for financial constraints, thus exposing them to financial hardships. Some of the management noted:

“I think for us, the secret was the nature of the majority of the members. Like said before, most of our members are government employees and therefore their monthly subscriptions continued to come throughout” (KII III)

“And then in a small way, I must also say the civil service whom we likely serve, they were not laid off. The government did not have layoffs compared to private institutions.” (KII VII)

“Our members from the hospitality sectors, hotels were closed. Closed for a very long time. So, somebody was working in the hotels sector. They were sent home. So may be first month they had salary, second month the employer was not able to pay, then they come for their savings” (KII I)

Open Mindedness and Quick Adaptability

It was also evident that the swiftness to adjust to the prevailing conditions created by the pandemic enabled the CFIs to maneuver the turbulence of the COVID-19 period. Thus, SACCOs had to quickly adjust their plans, programs and schedules to ensure they adhered with the regulatory provisions. The provisions included are: social distancing, mandatory and regular sanitization, mandatory hand washing, mandatory use of PPEs, the dusk to dawn curfews and later the vaccinations. The respondents noted that the regulatory measures were announced and implemented immediately without giving them any time to adjust. Some of the regulations forced the CFIs to embrace remote working and virtual operations. The some of the participants had the following to note:

“So the only other thing that I can say now in relation to the question is that we must, at all times, be ready to change with those circumstances. Yeah! That’s flexibility. There’s a business word they use there. I don’t know, it’s called what? Agile?”. (KIIX)

“I think openness and willingness to change, to change our way of doing business and taking bold decisions very fast.Yes, so I think adaptability and we have swiftness in making decisions”. (KIIV)

“Yes, very flexible. Yeah. So that, you know, we do, we are not overtakenagile decision-making to adapt to rapidly changing circumstances” (KIIVI)

Adherence to Healthcare Provisions

The CFIs also noted that they strictly adhered to the healthcare provisions to cushion some of their staff who had to work from offices. Such healthcare services included provision of PPEs, and washing systems, sanitizers and social distancing in the offices. Some also noted that they enforced vaccination on all their staff in efforts to minimize the spread of the virus amongst themselves and out in the community.

“Then the issue of public masks came in. We acquired masks for our staff members and sanitizers for the same, we put in measures, aaa those floor markers for social distancing. And also, now spacing the offices..... So that we moved some people out so that we have now that social distances, which was a new façade back then” (KII I)

“A lot of things had to change, for example social distances meant that many staffs could not come to office. The few who came had to be in the right PPEs, the masks, and had to sanitize regularly. When the vaccines came, all staff were encouraged to get the jab”. (KII II)

Effective Communication

Participants noted that effective communication between the management and management, management and staff, and institution and members ensured the peri and post pandemic success of SACCOs. The effectiveness of the communication was indicated by the transparency, timeliness and the relevance depending on the prevailing condition. Between management, the communication promoted agility in decision making and adaptability while between management and staff, the communication promoted collaboration, transparency and wellbeing of the staff. Additionally, effective communication with members of the CFIs,

promoted the trust of the members, and alleviated any fears surrounding their savings and dividends or deposits. Some of the respondents were quoted saying:

“We also diversified our investment portfolio and enhanced member communication to maintain trust and confidence.” (KII VIII)

“I think we also prioritized transparent and proactive communication with our members, keeping them informed about changes in services, safety measures, and support options available during the crisis and assuring them that everything is under control.” (KII IX)

“There's something that is normally called the going concern; and every time that we congregate with members, we always have to give them assurances that this entity is not falling tomorrow. Okay, it's called the coin coaster” (KIIX)

Strategy Post Covid-19

The participants were asked whether their CFIs have any resilience strategies after the pandemic. The results show that 85.71% of the sampled SACCOs have a resilience strategy, while 11.43% noted that they are back to the default setting. Only, 2.86% noted that they don't have any resilience strategy post COVID-19. Figure 1 summarizes the results. The same proportion (85.71%) of the participants noted that there is a need for an improved resilience strategy and suggested the need to improve the existing model.

Figure 1: Post-COVID-19 Resilience Strategy

When asked of the strategies they have, the participants noted various strategies as summarized in Table 7 of the strategies highlighted, digitization and innovation of new products and services topped the list representing 28.57% and 25.71% of the responses respectively. 11.43% of the SACCOs noted that they have come up with a slogan “Mteja Kwanza”, translated to “Customer first”. Other notable strategies noted included institutional strengthening and membership growth patronizing products and services increasing members’ savings.

Table 7: Post COVID-19 Resilience Strategy

Category	Frequency	Percentage
Digitization	10	28.57
Innovation (new products and services)	9	25.71
Customer first	4	11.43
Institutional strengthening	3	8.57
Membership growth	3	8.57
Patronizing products and services	2	5.71
Increasing members savings	2	5.71
Training of members on savings and investments	2	5.71
Investments into other businesses	2	5.71
Business continuity plan	2	5.71
Improved risk management	1	2.86

Discussion

The findings on factors of resilience during the pandemic suggest that older CFIs, with more established histories, tended to allocate larger loan amounts to members during the pandemic compared to younger CFIs. This association underscores the importance of organizational maturity and resilience in responding to economic challenges posed by COVID-19 pandemic. Corporate Financial Institutions with longer operating histories may have greater capacity and experience to manage larger loan portfolios during times of crisis. The study thus provides valuable insights into the relationship between CFI age and loan distribution during COVID-19, emphasizing the role of organizational maturity and resilience in shaping lending practices within cooperative financial institutions amidst challenging economic conditions.

The findings on association between membership size and resilience of CFIs during COVID-19 pandemic, underscore the influence of CFI membership size on lending practices during the COVID-19 crisis. SACCOs with larger memberships demonstrated greater capacity to extend larger loan amounts, potentially reflecting organizational resilience and resource availability. This association has implications for CFI management strategies and member engagement approaches during times of economic uncertainty. The study therefore highlights useful intuitions into the relationship between CFI membership size and loan issuance patterns during Covid-19, emphasizing the role of organizational scale in shaping lending activities within cooperative financial institutions especially during turbulence of uncertain economic dynamics.

The study highlights the diverse funding sources utilized by CFI and how they might have impacted on loan distribution by the CFI during the pandemic. While strong associations are observed based on measures like Phi coefficient and Cramer's V, caution is warranted due to the lack of statistical significance in the Chi-Square tests, indicating that these associations may not be causally linked. Further research could explore additional factors influencing CFIs' resilience and loan distribution, considering the complex interplay between funding sources, operational challenges, and member needs.

A further analysis of the relationship between the sector of operation of the CFI and their resilience showed significant association. The significance of the association identified implies that specific sectors of CFI operations exhibit distinct loan distribution behaviors during the pandemic. CFI operating within different sectors may face unique challenges or adopt varying strategies in disbursing loans to members based on their operational focus.

Understanding the relationship between the CFI sector of operation and their resilience with regards to extension of credit facilities can inform targeted interventions or policy adjustments to support CFI based on their operational context. Policymakers and stakeholders can leverage these insights to tailor support mechanisms that address sector-specific challenges and enhance overall CFI resilience. For instance, CFI whose membership mainly comprised people working in private transport, tourism and hospitality industries faced totally different challenges compared to CFI whose membership mainly comprised people in the civil service. The findings therefore underscore the importance of sector-specific analysis in understanding CFI loan distribution behaviors, offering valuable implications for policymakers and practitioners seeking to bolster the resilience of cooperative financial institutions in challenging economic contexts.

The study established that the critical success factors among the CFIs as they maneuvered the pandemic included Technology adoption advancement, Status of membership, Open mindedness and quick adaptability, adherence to healthcare provisions and effective communication. These initiatives can be as absorptive capacity, adaptive capacity or transformative capacities. Adaptive capacities are the actions that the CFIs took to moderate or buffer themselves against the effects of the pandemic without forcing the institutions into major changes. In this sense therefore adaptive capacity could include the adherence to the healthcare guidelines and recommendation as stipulated by the Ministry of Health. The findings of this study thus align with Gundertofte, Thur, and Torm, (2022), is a social protection for the staff members and such comprises of such initiatives as provision of sanitizers, PPEs, hand washing stations, promoting social distances and enabling some staff members to work from home during the pandemic. Adaptive resilience factors include those initiatives such as technology adoption and advancements were notable among the majority of the CFI. This finding aligns with that of Gundertofte and colleagues who noted that adaptive capacity included adoption of channels of communication that would see Information Workers Associations disseminating information about Covid-19 and training of members of staffs (Gundertofte et al., 2022).

Transformative capacity on the other hand is characterized with migration which in this case could include migration from manual ways of doing things to digital models of doing business. Most CFIs noted that the pandemic necessitated digital transformation to ensure continuity of their businesses. Such transformation involved amendment of bylaws which then formalized virtual meeting and voting as well as service delivery. These findings coincide with those of Ridwansah, (2020) and McKillop & French, (2020) who found that most organizations developed innovative solutions to enhance their survival and continuity in business. On service delivery for example the CFIs adopted mobile and online technologies of loan application, processing and dispensation. In Bali, for example, 172 cooperatives initiated semi-online, online or digital technology financial services in 2019 while in 2020, 133 implemented the same strategy (Rustariyuni, et al., 2022). Consequently, the cooperatives experience efficiencies in transaction processes while minimizing risk of spreading the virus.

Conclusion: Improved resilient business model for Cooperative Financial Institutions in Kenya

A consideration of the critical success factors such as status of membership, open mindedness and quick adaptability, effective communication, business continuity planning and technology advancement, and shows that an improved model should integrate these aspects.

Status of membership

According to the research findings, SACCOs whose members have consistent income flow and are subjected to the check off system, such as government employees, were less impacted by pandemic related economic disruptions. CFIs with large membership often have a broad financial base and more resilient financial reservoir as compared to CFIs with small membership. Additionally, big membership implies a higher number of active borrowers and thus enhances financial sustainability (Yitayaw, 2021). The three dimensions of CFIs membership which can directly influence their resilience are the influence of membership on economies of scale, risk diversification and member engagement.

In the case of the CFIs membership is a critical factor of economies of scale because the membership size of a CFI for examples can have a direct impact on its long-term sustainability and resilience more so in times of economic crises. A CFI with a large membership is more likely to be stronger and stable and therefore more resilience. Many organizations count on membership growth and improved partnership for CFIs. Substantial benefits are associated with size of membership in CFIs. Firstly, growth in membership is directly and positively linked with growth of the cooperative society. In other words, when a CFI's membership grows drastically and steadily, it creates the impression that the CFI is attractive in terms of the products and service they offer and that the CFI is trust worthy in term of the welfare of the members (Retegi, & Igartua, 2023). Secondly large membership increases the inflow and outflow of cash as more members will be encouraged to deposit their savings or shares. Additionally, more people will apply for loans and in so doing, the CFI will generate more revenue from interests charged on the loan. From the member's deposits, the CFI's can expand their investments, services and products and thus grow financially and in terms of capital (Navy Federal Credit Union, 2022). Thirdly, large membership gives the CFIs a large pool of human resource from which they can access diversified human resources to manage day-to-day operations.

It is therefore critical for CFIs to invest on strategies which can see them recruit more members so that they can enjoy economies of scale. In so doing, they will reduce their operational costs while at the same time generate more revenue from member deposits for savings or share capital. The revenue generated can then be invested to earn the CFIs more revenue from which they can enhance their resilience.

Open Mindedness and Quick Adaptability

This study established that the management of the CFIs were open minded to the new norm including remote work arrangement, digital transformation, adherence to health guidelines enforced to mitigate the spread of COVID-19, and virtual meeting including the Annual General Meeting (AGM). The swift shift of model of business operation from physical to virtual was one of the main critical success factor cited by all the CFIs which participated in the study. Quick adaptability allows organizations to stay ahead of the curve and remain competitive in volatile markets (Shani, 2020). For example, the the Co-operative Bank (Co-op Bank) quickly enhanced its digital banking platform to cater to the surge in demand for online services. They introduced a mobile banking app with expanded functionalities, allowing customers to access a wide range of banking services remotely. Additionally, Co-op Bank and Harambee SACCO launched various financial support measures, such as loan restructuring and payment holidays, to assist members facing financial difficulties due to the pandemic. Similarly, Stima SACCO transitioned to digital platforms for transactions and communications. They implemented an online loan application system and digital member meetings, which allowed for seamless operations despite movement restrictions. This ability

to navigate the crisis by swiftly implementing new strategies and technologies was instrumental in their survival and continued operation.

Earlier studies indicate the open mindedness and adaptability particularly during economic market disruption is a critical resilience factor that organizations not only need but must be readily to embrace and implement. Boylan, and Turner (2017) found that open-mindedness involves being receptive to new ideas, perspectives, and ways of doing things. Akgün, and Keskin, (2014) adds that flexibility and adaptability encourages a growth mindset, where individuals view challenges as opportunities for learning and development. Stima SACCO's and Unaitas SACCO, initiative to provide virtual workshops on financial literacy programs and business continuity planning to support members in adapting to the new economic realities.

The examples above indicate that organizations that prioritize continuous learning and skill development are better equipped to adapt to changing circumstances and overcome obstacles. In a rapidly changing business environment, organizations must be able to adapt quickly to external factors such as technological advancements, regulatory changes, and market disruptions.

Effective Communication

The findings noted that internal and external and effective communication between the CFIs management and staffs and their customers, and other stakeholders ensured efficient decision-making and assured their customers and members of the status of the CFI. Various studies have singled out effective communication as a key function that promotes loyalty among staffs, board members as well and the members of the CFIs. In their study, Kim (2021), noted that clear communication ensures that everyone in the organization understands its goals, strategies, and expectations. Chewning, Lai, and Doerfel, (2013) added that transparent communication builds trust between leaders and employees. This trust is crucial during times of crisis when employees look to leaders for guidance and reassurance. This helps in preventing misunderstandings and minimizes uncertainty, allowing for quicker responses to emerging threats. During crises, communication becomes even more critical. Resilient organizations have crisis communication plans in place to ensure that accurate information is communicated promptly to all stakeholders (Chewning, Lai, &Doerfel, (2013).

In Kenya, CFIs such as SACCOs, effectively leverage communication to enhance their resilience. The pandemic necessitated a rapid shift in how these institutions operated and engaged with their members. Kimisitu Sacco maintained regular communication with its members by sending out frequent updates on their operations, financial health, and the measures taken to protect members' investments. They utilized multiple channels, including emails, their website, and social media, to provide information about branch operations, health and safety protocols, and the availability of online services (Kimisitu Sacco Annual Report, 2020). Sheria SACCO focused on member support by providing financial relief options, such as loan restructuring and payment holidays. They effectively communicated these options through text messages, social media, and their website. Additionally, Stima SACCO engaged in community support by donating to COVID-19 relief efforts, which they communicated to their members to highlight their commitment to the community. As noted in their annual report, they indicated that effective communication was key in maintaining the trust of the members amidst the uncertainties that came with the pandemic (Sheria Sacco Annual Report, 2020).

The examples above demonstrate how proactive and adaptive communication strategies can play a pivotal role in crisis management for financial institutions. By maintaining transparency, enhancing digital communication channels, personalizing messages, supporting employees, and engaging in community initiatives, CFIs are able to sustain operations, reassure stakeholders, and emerge more resilient.

Business Continuity Plans

Establishing a Business Continuity Unit (BCU) can ensure that critical business functions can continue during and after a disruption, such as natural disasters, cyber-attacks, or pandemics. A BCU is a dedicated team or department within an organization responsible for developing, implementing, and managing the business continuity plan (BCP). According to Fani and Subriadi (2019) Effective BCPs are characterized with comprehensive risk assessment and business impact analysis, response and recovery strategies, resource management, communication plan, testing training and documentation and maintenance

The pandemic however found most CFIs in Kenya with neither BCU nor BCP. Many Cooperative Financial Institutions (CFIs) in Kenya faced significant challenges during COVID-19 due to a lack of BCUs and BCPs. Harambee Sacco for example faced liquidity issues due to increased loan defaults, decreased deposits and increased withdrawals. The lack of a pre-existing BCP meant they were unprepared for the sudden economic shock. The SACCO had to hastily implement measures such as loan restructuring and negotiating with creditors to maintain operations. The lack of a structured continuity plan led to inefficiencies and delayed responses to members' needs. Mwalimu National SACCO struggled with communication and operational continuity. Many members were unaware of relief measures due to ineffective communication strategies. Consequently, they had to developed ad-hoc solutions to improve member communication and support. However, the absence of a formal BCP led to inconsistent service delivery and member dissatisfaction. Stima SACCO faced issues similar to other SACCOs, such as disruptions in service delivery and financial stress. They were relatively better prepared and managed to implement a digital transformation quickly. However, their initial lack of a comprehensive BCP meant the transition was slow and reactive rather than proactive, leading to some operational hiccups.

On the other hand, Kenya Police SACCO leveraged its BCU to transition to remote working arrangements and enhance its digital platforms, enabling members to access services online. They also introduced financial relief programs, such as loan restructuring and moratoriums, to support members affected by the pandemic. The proactivity measures taken by Kenya Police SACCO ensured continuous service delivery and member support, helping to mitigate the financial impact of COVID-19 on its members. Additionally, the BCU at Equity Bank developed and implemented comprehensive plans to handle various crises, including the COVID-19 pandemic. The unit facilitated remote work for employees, enhanced digital banking services, and ensured continuous customer support, demonstrating the bank's preparedness and adaptability.

The COVID-19 pandemic highlighted the importance of resilience and preparedness for CFIs in Kenya. While some institutions managed to adapt, many struggled due to the absence of structured BCUs and BCPs. The experiences during the pandemic have hopefully underscored the need for these institutions to develop and implement comprehensive continuity plans to better navigate future crises.

Technology Advances

Leveraging financial technology (fintech) enhanced SACCO's resilience by improving operational efficiency, expanding access to financial services, and enhancing customer experiences. The findings indicate that the adoption of operational and service delivery technologies contributed to SACCOs' resilience and success. Various technologies including Digital Payments and Mobile Banking, Data Analytics and Digital Lending Platforms can help enhance the resilience of CFIs.

Digital payments and mobile banking are two prominent examples of fintech that have enabled remote transactions for whichever reason, whether, lending or borrowing, buying or selling, or just account management. M-Pesa is, a mobile money platform with over 20 million active users, provided by the Kenya telecommunication giant; Safaricom PLC enables users to perform a wide range of financial transactions via their mobile phones. Mobile banking demonstrates the profound potential of fintech to reshape financial services globally, offering increased convenience, accessibility, and efficiency which are most paramount for resilience in periods of economic disruption for example COVID-19, which limited physical contact.

Data Analytics specifically involves examining raw data to draw conclusions about that information. It uses statistical, computational, and machine learning techniques to analyze data sets and identify patterns, trends, and insights. Data analytics has the potential of reducing the burden of bad debts which has been a serious problem with most CFIs. For example, M-Shwari, a product by Safaricom and Commercial Bank of Africa (CBA), uses data analytics to assess the creditworthiness of its users based on their mobile phone usage and transaction history. This has enabled M-Shwari to extend micro-loans to millions of Kenyans who lack traditional credit histories, thereby enhancing financial inclusion and institutional resilience (Strusani, & Hounbonon, 2019). Data analytics can be applied in business to enhancing customer experiences, optimizing operations, and driving strategic decision-making more so in times of crisis like the COVID-19 pandemic.

In the context of fintech, lending platforms refer to online platforms that use technology to facilitate the borrowing and lending process. These platforms connect borrowers directly with lenders, often bypassing traditional financial intermediaries such as banks. This can result in faster loan approvals, lower costs, and the ability to serve a broader range of customers, including those who may not have access to traditional banking services. Consequently, lending platforms can provide significant solutions to CFIs whose main business involves lending (Daley, 2024). In Kenya, Tala Mobile Lending for example provides microloans to individuals in emerging markets using mobile technology. Adopting Fintech lending platforms helps CFIs adapt to changing market conditions, meet the needs of their members more effectively, and ensure long-term sustainability.

Aside from fintech, technological advances facilitate the adaption of the other four pillars of an improved resilient business model for CFIs. For example, effective communication during crises will likely utilize multiple digital and online channels from email, social media and traditional media. Because technology plays such a pivotal role in advancing a resilient model for CFIs, the researcher is developing a paper that discusses this topic more extensively.

In conclusion, an improved resilient business model for CFIs based on adopting new technologies, business models, and approaches will enable many CFIs to continue operations, support their members, and maintain financial stability in the face of unprecedented challenges.

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